

26th Southeast Conference for
Languages, Literatures and Film

On Phonetic Interference: What are the Obstacles to Fonphone

Learners of French?

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*This work builds on an undergraduate project, "L'interférence linguistique: le cas de Fon et du français Bénin," initially conducted during my undergraduate studies at the Department of European Studies, University of Ibadan, 2020. The present work has been substantially revised and expanded.

Abstract

The question of linguistic interference has become an increasingly prominent area of inquiry in applied linguistics and second language acquisition research. It is widely acknowledged that the success of teaching and learning a second language is significantly shaped by the phonological, lexical, and syntactic structures of a previously acquired language.

The present study aims to examine phonetic interference, focusing on the pronunciation challenges faced by Fon-speaking learners of French in the Republic of Benin, a West African country. Using a mixed-methods research design, the study was carried out with 30 final-year students from three primary schools in the Zou region of the country. Using Adobe Audition Software, data were collected through the pronunciation tests of 63 French words (including minimal pairs). The analyses were done using Calvet's theory (1993), which highlights the different levels of linguistic interference: phonetic, lexical, morphological, syntactic, etc. (Kannas 252).

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This approach is pertinent in contemporary studies, as seen in Martins (2007) and in Sadoun and Tounsi (2022).

The findings show certain systematic pronunciation issues resulting from the influence of the learners' native language—Fon—on their acquisition of the French language. This study contributes to a better understanding of the phenomenon of language contact in multilingual educational settings and suggests pedagogical strategies to navigate these difficulties.

Keywords: phonetic interference, Fon, Benin, language

Reference

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